

**INTEGRATION OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL MICRO MECHANICS
PROCEDURES INTO THE DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF
COMPOSITE MATERIALS**

John J. Kibler, Ph.D.
Director of Engineering
Materials Sciences Corporation
Union Meeting Corporate Center
Blue Bell, PA 19422

ABSTRACT

As a result of years of teaching the design and analysis of composite materials, a computer program, CLASS, has been developed which incorporates all of the necessary features to permit accurate, and complete easy analysis of composite materials in a very general sense. This paper describes the fundamental theoretical capabilities which have been incorporated into CLASS, along with the reasons for their inclusion. As a result of day to day utilization of this program within Materials Sciences Corporation, the code has continued to be expanded to include practical analysis capabilities which make it the code of choice for many engineering applications analyses related to composite materials.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Laminates; Properties; Analytical modeling; Progressive Failure; Computer Programs.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Many solutions to practical composite materials problems have been obtained using micro-mechanics and have been published in the literature throughout the past few decades. Of these, perhaps lamination theory, failure criteria, and theories for predicting the properties of unidirectional composites have received the greatest attention. However, many other useful and practical solutions have been obtained for modeling composite materials. The engineer who is first faced with designing a composite structure can become quickly overwhelmed at the complexity of the task.

The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate that combining available analytical tools into a single user friendly code will provide a tremendous computational

properties, and engineering terms is necessary. However, close familiarity with the analytical methods programmed within the code are not necessary.

Assuming that the engineer has a design problem which allows options relative to fiber and matrix type, constituent volume fractions and fiber orientations, the variables can seem endless. Deciding which material combinations may be best for a given application is formidable indeed.

Approaching the material design process from an experimental point of view may eventually get to a solution, but not until many combinations of materials are fabricated and tested. Analytical synthesis of the composite properties can provide insight relative to the materials which may be best suited for the application. However, synthesizing composite material properties requires an understanding of many micromechanics problems and their solutions. This generally requires many hours of study and programming to get the required properties.

The development of CLASS has been focused upon incorporating the correct available analytical results for a number of problems into a single code which contains an easily understood user interface. At the same time, the code does not constrain the user into specific configurations or materials. Key to this capability is the inclusion of a material property data base which can be maintained by the engineer so that current and necessary constituent properties, or layer properties are available at all times.

2.0 DISCUSSION

The future utilization of composite materials to their full potential will require that usable and flexible analytical tools exist for the applications engineers as well as the materials engineers.

Analysis of composites has made great advances as we move into the 1990's. These advances need to be available to engineers who are analyzing and designing with these complex materials. The presence of a personal computer or computer terminal in nearly every office, plus codes such as CLASS can provide that capability. Engineers can now use these complex micro mechanics methods in a transparent interface while being assured that the best available tools are being applied to the problem. At the same time, these codes must warn the engineer when he or she is attempting to use the code for a problem for which it was not intended.

The CLASS code was written as a teaching aid to demonstrate the computation of both layer and laminate properties of composite materials, figure 1. It was intended for engineers who had very little computer experience, and is therefore entirely user interactive and menu driven. The code's popularity in a classroom environment led to developing strength predictions, layer cracking, temperature dependent properties, particulate calculations and stress analysis capability within the code. With the increased popularity of single user micro computers, the code has been becoming popular with practicing engineers who desire the ability to evaluate a number

2.1 Code Overview One main concern was focused upon throughout the code development. Namely, if one supplies a general purpose analysis code to the engineering community, one cannot control the user's input, and must guard against the old adage; "garbage-in" equals "garbage-out." Consequently, the code contains a high level of error checking in an attempt to insure that the user is at least modeling real materials. CLASS will not permit storing thermodynamically inadmissible materials, nor analysis of materials with negative thicknesses or unrealistic volume fractions. In addition, when particle to matrix moduli ratios are large, or particle volume fractions are large, warning messages appear to warn the user that the solutions may be approximate.

CLASS was written in a combination of "C" and Assembly language for IBM compatible personal computers. It was written with growth in mind, and as such can be modified relatively easily to include new analysis capabilities as they become desirable. The code currently runs without overlays or special memory management tools, and can more than double in size before these techniques need to be invoked.

CLASS predicts the elastic constants, thermal expansions, strengths, thermal conductivities, and stiffness and compliance matrix terms, as well as internal stress states of laminated composite materials. The user may start the analysis by supplying fiber and matrix properties, or by supplying layer properties.

Many of the code's features are discussed in the following sections. Note however, that details of the coded analytical results are not discussed. The programmed analytical formulations are well documented in the literature, and are referenced for the interested reader.

The following sections discuss topics included in CLASS: 1. Temperature dependent data base management of fiber, matrix, particle, and layer properties; 2. Composite material descriptions data file; 3. Composite cylinders assemblage for transversely isotropic fibers imbedded in a transversely isotropic matrix; 4. Imperfect bonding between fiber and matrix within the fiber bundle; 5. Differential scheme approaches for calculating the properties of particle reinforced matrix materials; 6. Simple representation of laminate description, including hybrids and fiber/matrix combinations; 7. Laminate property calculations; 8. Strength calculations using the popular failure theories, Max Stress, Max Strain, Tsai-Wu, and Hashin's plane stress interaction theories; 9. Strengths based upon first ply failure, as well as sequential ply cracking until first fiber failure; 10. Point stress analysis of

Figure 1 - CLASS

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COMPOSITE MATERIALS ANALYSIS SYSTEM

options are -

1 - CONSTITUENT/LAYER PROPERTIES
2 - COMPUTE LAYER PROPERTIES
3 - COMPUTE LAMINATE PROPERTIES
F1 - Help Screens

'ESC' to exit codes

constructed laminate, including: applied temperature changes, generalized applied forces, and mixed force/strain loading.

2.2 Data Base of Constituent Properties CLASS allows the user to maintain a complete data base of constituent properties. These properties, including definitions of the user's standard laminate constructions, then form the primary input values for conducting laminate analyses.

2.2.1 Temperature Dependent Constituents Constituent properties are stored in several data base files. Each constituent file, i.e. fiber, matrix, particle, and layer, may contain an arbitrary number of records, and each record may contain properties for an arbitrary number of temperatures. Memory is allocated dynamically, so the maximum number of records and temperatures is dependent upon the available memory in the operating system. With the exception of particles (which must currently be isotropic), all constituents may be transversely isotropic. The user must supply elastic constants, expansion coefficients, thermal conductivities, and strengths for each constituent.

Standard engineering elastic constants are prompted for on the record screen, but options exist for defining the constituent's bulk modulus, and for inputting delta l/l characteristics rather than temperature dependent secant expansion coefficients. Also built into the code is the ability to translate the stress free reference temperature for a given constituent to a new reference temperature, thus allowing mixing of reference temperatures in the analysis sections of the code.

The code operates with any CONSISTENT set of units of measure. The user must be careful in this regard, if SI units are used for several of the input constituent properties, then these constituents should only be combined with other constituents having the SAME units of measure. This is particularly important relative to defining layer thicknesses to be used in the laminate formulation.

2.2.2 Composite Material Descriptions Data File Laminate description is generally a burden in any laminate analysis code. Materials, thicknesses, and orientations need to be defined for each layer in the laminate. In CLASS, this burden has been largely overcome by using a text description for the laminate, and allowing that description to be stored in a laminate description file. Laminates are defined as shown in figure 2. Note that the description string "reads" very much like standard laminate nomenclature, and therefore is very easy to input to the code. Once a thickness or material is defined, it remains the default for the coming layers until the value is changed. CLASS also allows the user to define a layer by describing the fiber, matrix, and fiber volume fraction of the layer, in which case the layer properties are computed during the laminate analysis.

The user may specify repeating patterns of a laminate by enclosing the repeating pattern within square brackets. When square brackets are used, the definitions remain in effect only within the current level of the square brackets, thus re-definition of the default values is not necessary upon leaving the square brackets. Repeating patterns may be nested up to ten levels deep.

Adding a "/S" within a nesting level will create a symmetric pattern within the nested brackets, and a "/S" at the end of the laminate string will create a symmetric laminate. Since very complicated unbalanced, unsymmetric, hybrid laminates can be created and analyzed, the code interprets the laminate description string, and then shows the user precisely what each layer of the laminate will be. By checking the code's interpretation of the laminate description from the display screen, the user can insure that the desired laminate is indeed being analyzed.

2.3 Synthesis of Matrix and Layer Properties Laminates are formed from layer properties. Layer properties can be either input directly by the user, or computed by combining particles and a matrix to form a reinforced matrix, or combining fibers and a matrix to form a fiber reinforced layer material. In many cases the appropriate approach is to compute the layer

Figure 2. Laminate Description

EXPLANATION OF LAMINATE DESCRIPTION

This code formulates a GENERAL LAMINATE using classical laminated plate theory. It is important to understand the nomenclature used in the code to define the laminate being analyzed. A shorthand description is used to identify the laminate as follows:

```

/M i/      following layers are material `i' (default = 1 )
/T j/      following layers are thickness `j' (default = .1)
/XXX/      orientation of layer is `XXX' degrees
/S         at end of input means laminate is symmetric
/C         at end means to continue on next line (max # = 7)
[../../..]N repeats pattern in [...] N times
           maximum number of layers is 500

```

```

M1/T.005/0/45/-45/90/S      ( 8 layers)
M2/T.007/[0/60/-60]6/S     (36 layers)

```

The Following are equivalent ---

- a) M1/T.01/0/45/-45/0/45/-45/M2/0/60/-60/T.1/0/C
0/T.01/-60/60/0/M1/-45/45/0/-45/45/0
- b) M1/T.01/[0/45/-45]2/M2/0/60/-60/T.1/0/S

properties from the fiber and matrix. The predicted properties, particularly strengths, should be edited to reflect any test data which might be available and applicable for the layer in question. Thus the code can be used to predict those properties which are not available and edited to reflect those properties which might be available through testing.

2.3.1 Properties of Particle Reinforced Matrix Materials Particles in a matrix are becoming increasingly important. In many cases the engineer can tailor the matrix properties to those desirable by adding particles. Particles can range from short fibers, to spherical particles, to flat, penny shaped discs. These analytical models are valid only for dilute concentrations of particles whose properties are not significantly different from the matrix.

The differential scheme, reference 1, has been encoded using the solutions for spheres, needles, and platelets, (references 2 and 3). Employing the differential scheme enables extrapolating the available analytical results to larger particle volume fractions. Limitations are not yet known, pending experimental data to define properties.

2.3.2 Unidirectional Material Properties When combining fiber and matrix to form a layer, CLASS utilizes the general composite cylinders assemblage formulation, references 4 and 5. Transversely isotropic constituents can be handled with this approach, and bounds on the elastic constants and thermal expansion coefficients are obtained, see references 6 and 7. Christensen's model, reference 8, for transverse moduli are also obtained since this approach gives results which fall between the arbitrary phase geometry lower bound and the composite cylinders assemblage upper bound. The advanced user is given options for which transverse bounds to save.

Strengths of the unidirectional material are estimated using the failure models postulated in reference 9. It must be emphasized that layer strengths are only estimated, as no one has yet derived a failure criterion which applies fully to matrix dominated modes of a layer. Fiber dominated modes in tension and compression are addressed in reference 9, but interface conditions and stress concentrations associated with the transverse layer strengths require that predicted strengths be considered as estimates only.

2.3.3 Imperfect Bonding Between Fiber and Matrix In many applications, the fibers will not bond perfectly to the surrounding matrix material. This is true for carbon matrix materials, as well as for many metal matrix systems. Consequently, the fiber-matrix interface is an important parameter in the analytical model. Hashin, reference 10, has proposed an analytical approach to modeling the interface in a manner which is amenable to definition of the interface condition ranging from 0.0, no interface, to 1.0, fully bonded interface. This approach is included in CLASS, where the user is asked to define the interface efficiency in transverse tension, transverse shear, and axial shear. The values of efficiency can range from 0.0 (fully unbonded) to 1.0 (fully bonded).

2.4 Laminate Analysis Given a data base of layer properties, or fibers and matrices from which layer properties can be constructed, the user is now ready to construct laminates. CLASS requires that the user define the layer material, layer thickness, and layer orientation. This is accomplished through a laminate description string, as described in the following sections.

Once the laminate is formulated, the code allows computation of strengths as well as the evaluation of laminate response to generalized point loading conditions.

2.4.1 Description of Laminate A shorthand notation has been programmed to allow specification of the laminate construction with text that closely follows industry standard specifications.

The user constructs a laminate by defining the layer material, layer thickness, and layer orientation. Since CLASS allows fully general laminates, each layer can be specified with these three parameters. If the material type or layer

thickness is not specified, then CLASS assumes that the current layer is the same material and thickness as the previously defined layer. Thus, material type and layer thickness need only be specified initially and when changes occur within the laminate. The maximum number of layers allowed has been arbitrarily set at five hundred.

One of the main strengths of CLASS is the shorthand notation used to specify a laminate. The laminate is defined by a string of orientations separated by "/". The material type for following layers is placed ahead of a layer orientation as "/Mi/", and the thickness is specified as "/Tj/". A 0/45/-45/90 symmetric laminate of material "3" from the layers file, with layer thicknesses of 0.007 units would be specified as:

M3/T0.007/0/45/-45/90/S

The "/S" signifies that the laminate is symmetric about the mid-plane. Repeating patterns of layers are specified by placing the repeating pattern definition within square brackets, and following the closing square bracket with a number representing the number of times the pattern is to be repeated. For example, eight layers of material "5" at 0/90, on a core of material "6" oriented as 0/60/-60 (repeated 5 times) could be specified as (assuming $t=0.007$)

T0.007/[M5/0/90]4/[M6/0/60/-60]5

In addition to the above, the user has several other variables which can be used to define the laminate. These are: FIB to define the fiber in a layer, MTX to define the matrix into which the FIBER is imbedded, and VOL defines the volume fraction of fiber in the matrix. Layers can be defined during the analysis. Also, TREF and TEMP define the reference temperature and material temperature to be used for the current analysis.

The code interprets the input strings, displays the lay-up on a layer by layer basis, defines layer numbers, layer thicknesses, and layer orientations for the entire laminate. Layer identification name, (and fiber name, matrix name, and fiber volume fraction) give positive evidence of the materials to be combined into a laminate. This is provided as a check for the user before initiating calculations.

2.4.2 Laminate Properties The laminate analysis follows the general laminated plate theory found in references 11, 12 13 and 14. The user can specify a different material, layer thickness and layer orientation for each layer in the laminate, if desired. General laminate constructions can be handled, with full coupling of all stiffness and expansion terms. Thermal Conductivities are computed using the approach outlined in reference 15.

The laminate properties are displayed after computations, and the initial display presents the "engineering" constants, Figure 3 as defined by the mid-plane response of the laminate. These properties are presented regardless of whether the laminate possesses significant coupling terms in it's stiffness matrix or not. Another screen presents the laminate "A,B,D" matrices. This

Figure 3 - CLASS Predicted Laminate Properties

```

LAMINATE THERMOELASTIC PROPERTIES      Temperature: 0
MATERIAL IS : T300 (epoxy) / EPOXY / VF= .6

      E l a s t i c      C o n s t a n t s

In-Plane Properties                      Bending Properties
E xx ( 0) = 5.3238E+01                   D xx = 3.7959E+00
E yy (90) = 5.3238E+01                   D yy = 8.9748E-01
G xy = 2.0232E+01                        D xy = 6.6894E-01
Nu x,y = 0.3157                          <- Note: x,y = Load,Strain

Laminate Density Rho = 1.57

      T h e r m a l      P r o p e r t i e s

Thermal Expansions                      Thermal Conductivities
alpha xx ( 0) = 1.8548E-06                K xx = 137.5
alpha yy (90) = 1.8548E-06                K yy = 137.5
alpha xy = 0                               K xy = 0
k xx = 0                                    K zz = 50
k yy = 0
k xy = 0

```

screen should be consulted to determine if there are coupling terms that exist in the laminate analyzed.

2.4.3 Strength Calculations Strengths can be calculated using several failure criteria, figure 4, see references 16 and 17. Once the laminate properties have been computed, strength estimates can be obtained, figure 5. Initial strength calculations are based upon first ply failure, using the ply strength properties stored in the LAYERS file, or computed during the analysis.

Strengths are calculated for each of the principal loading directions, and listed assuming no applied temperatures. Additionally, CLASS will compute "first fiber failure" strengths. First fiber failure strengths are computed by allowing the laminate to fail sequentially in matrix failure modes until the next impending failure mode is a fiber failure. This strength calculation can be compared to an ultimate strength as opposed to a yielding stress level obtained by the first ply failure. Note, however, that in many cases the first ply failure and the first fiber failure stress levels are the same values.

2.4.4 Laminate Stress Analysis

In many cases, specific applied loads and temperatures are desirable to determine the load carrying capability of a laminate. The use can enter a section where specific loads can be applied to the laminate. Applied forces, moments, strains and curvatures may be applied. CLASS is unique in that it permits any combination of forces, moments, strains and curvatures to

Figure 4 - Failure

```

AVAILABLE FAILURE CRITERIA

1 - Maximum Stress
2 - Maximum Strain
3 - Plane Stress Interaction: Hashin
4 - Quadratic Interaction: Tsai-Wu

`ESC' for Composite menu

*** Default Criteria is ***

MAXIMUM STRESS

```

be applied to the laminate. It then solves the mixed boundary value problem to provide the laminate response.

Once the laminate mid-plane response is defined, CLASS will provide layer-by-layer stresses and strains, with the load and temperature induced components

separated. If the layer was formed from a fiber/matrix combination, the phase average fiber and matrix stresses are also computed.

CLASS maintains the minimum stress ratios for each layer, depending upon the selected failure criteria, and then defines the layer which controls the impending failure, along with the failure ratio. The applied loading conditions can be scaled to values which will induce laminate failure for the given point stress analysis. In this case, the temperature induced stress levels are held constant, and only the applied loadings are scaled to failure.

The point stress analysis section of the code allows the user to develop a full understanding of the load carrying capability of the laminate, along with a definition of how the laminate will begin to fail under the given load state.

The loading capability in CLASS provides the user with excellent capability to do point stress analysis. Mixed loading conditions of forces, strains, moments and curvatures can be applied to the laminate along with a uniform temperature change.

2.4.4.1 Sequential Ply Cracking After the initial loading is applied and the first ply failure loads are defined, the user has an option to crack the most highly stressed plies (in matrix mode) and to reapply loads.

Several points should be made relative to this option. The code defines the stress ratios for impending failures which would result in either matrix cracking or fiber failure. The minimum stress ratio for each ply is listed under the stress ratios. If the operator desires to allow the initial plies to crack, then the code examines the MATRIX modes of failure to define which ply will fail first in a matrix mode. The lowest stress ratio for matrix failure becomes the base ratio. The operator can then define, figure 6, how closely the other ratios should be examined to identify other plies to fail on that load increment.

Figure 5 - First Ply Strengths

Predicted Strengths

NOTE: These Strength Predictions Assume:
No Temperature, No Curvatures
MAXIMUM STRESS
Initial Loading.

UTS xx = 2.772E-01	UCS xx = 8.256E-02
UTS yy = 2.772E-01	UCS yy = 8.256E-02
USS xy = 6.361E-02	

Figure 6 - Sequential Ply Failures

Define How Much of COMPOSITE
Should be Cracked

Note: Only Matrix Failures
are Allowed

I - Next Group of Plies
F - Until First Fiber Failure
N - Crack All Plies (Netting)

*** Current Composite Status ***
0 Plies are Cracked.

Given a criteria for how many plies to crack, the code reformulates the laminate properties based on the cracked plies. The cracked plies are assumed to have near zero transverse and in-plane shear moduli, and zero Poisson's ratios, (fiber direction properties are not affected). The previous stress states are then re-applied to the laminate and the load at which the next failure will occur is re-computed. By following the strain response of the laminate, along with the loads for each successive ply failure, one can develop an estimate of the nonlinear stress strain response of the laminate.

In many cases the operator will find that once the first ply is allowed to crack, the load carrying capability is reduced to low enough levels that the total laminate would have failed on the initial loading. No provision is available for allowing plies to fail in a fiber failure mode, and to continue loading of the laminate. For philosophical reasons, the author prefers to define that a laminate has failed whenever any of the fibers have failed.

A word of caution regarding analysis of ply cracking. It is possible to develop laminates which can not sustain cracked plies without extreme reductions in the laminate stiffnesses. Such laminates will develop excessively large strains in those directions if loads are applied. The code attempts to check for large strains, and will provide a warning message if detected. The user should be cautious relative to these cases since the code is based upon infinitesimal strain theory and small deformations.

2.4.4.2 Fiber and Matrix Average Stresses When a layer is defined by a fiber/matrix/volume fraction combination, the code has sufficient information during the laminate analyses to be able to compute the phase average fiber and matrix stresses in the layer. This can be useful in determining the magnitude of stresses/strains within the constituents.

The micromechanical models provide a means for computing effective stiffnesses for various combinations of reinforcement, interface, and matrix. These bundle stiffnesses can be used to compute the composite stiffness. In order to estimate composite failure, it is necessary to have some measure of the stress state within the constituents. An approximate method for determining average stresses within fibers, matrix, and interphase is termed the phase average stress model. The phase average stress model can be applied to any of the micromechanical models discussed previously including continuous fibers, discontinuous fibers, or spherical particles. This model can be used to compute the local average stresses in the constituents.

3.0 SUMMARY

The CLASS code represents a desk top tool for the engineer to evaluate and construct laminate properties during a material design and evaluation study. At any time during an analysis session, the user can branch to various sections of the code to review the constituents and layer properties. The laminate formulation section has automatic checkpoints to summarize the laminate being analyzed at that time. In spite of both the "ease" and "speed" of these property calculations, the engineer does not have to feel that "back of the

envelop" calculations are being made. Rather, the engineer can feel that the best available analytical approaches are, in fact, being employed.

With the availability of codes like CLASS, the designer has available powerful tools for conducting design studies with composite materials. Handbook properties for composites of interest can be entered to be compared with special lay-ups for the structure of interest.

On the other hand, codes like CLASS add some complication to the design process. Since material properties for various laminated constructions are easy to compute, the designer should be required to always attempt to design both the material and structure at the same time. Both the material and structure should be optimized as a unit so that the best structural dimensions are defined along with each material reinforcement. Following a design process of this type, then weights and costs can be evaluated to determine the "best" overall design for a given application.

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5.0 BIOGRAPHY

Dr. Kibler received his Ph.D. from Lehigh University in 1969, where he studied fatigue crack growth in aluminum. He has been with Materials Sciences Corporation since 1973 and is Director of Engineering at MSC. He directs numerous materials research programs related to advanced composites and composite applications, including carbon-carbon, metal matrix, and ceramic matrix composites. He is well known for his work in minimizing processing risks in carbon-carbon materials. He has been a principal lecturer for MSC's courses on composite materials, which lead him to development of the CLASS code from its classroom version to current state.